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Plasma-enhanced atomic layer deposition of Al₂O₃ on graphene via an *in situ*-deposited interlayer

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ABSTRACT

A novel method has been developed for the deposition of high- κ dielectrics on graphene, which uses a nonstoichiometric aluminum oxide (AlOX) protective layer. This approach employs mild plasma conditions to directly grow a thin AlOX layer on graphene, followed by the deposition of aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) via plasma-enhanced atomic layer deposition (PEALD) without breaking the vacuum. A sub-3 nm AlOX layer provides effective protection for graphene and facilitates the formation of functional groups, thereby enabling the deposition of high-quality dielectrics without damaging the graphene. Top-gated graphene field-effect transistor (GFET) devices fabricated via this method demonstrated an electric field strength above 11 MV/cm and an equivalent oxide thickness (EOT) of less than 5 nm on a wafer scale. This deposition technique addresses a significant challenge in transitioning next-generation graphene-based electronics from the laboratory to industrial production.

1. Introduction

Graphene has demonstrated remarkable performance in various proof-of-concept devices [1–5], particularly when integrated with other materials to create functional devices. One important aspect is the integration of graphene with dielectric materials, which is essential for developing next-generation graphene-based electronic and photonic devices [4,6–8]. However, depositing dielectrics onto graphene is challenging because of its two-dimensional (2D) nature and sensitivity to damage [9–12].

Atomic layer deposition (ALD) has become the preferred technique for growing dielectrics on graphene because of its precise control of thickness and uniformity at the atomic scale [9,10]. Thermal (water-based) and plasma-enhanced ALD (PEALD) processes have been investigated for this purpose. Thermal ALD typically requires pretreatment of the graphene surface to achieve uniform dielectric coverage due to the hydrophobic and chemically inert nature of graphene [9,11–14]. In thermal ALD, various strategies, such as chemical modification of graphene, e-beam evaporation of thin metals followed by natural oxidation

[15–17], low-temperature ALD with extended dosing [18,19], and the use of self-assembled monolayer templates [7,20] have been proposed to initiate dielectric growth. These methods can be effective in promoting uniform growth and improving the adhesion of dielectrics. However, they often introduce additional preparation steps that are not *in situ* and increase the complexity of the process. Furthermore, their complexity and tendency to result in thicker dielectric stacks may limit their practicality for large-scale production, especially for the down-scaling of devices. Other studies have demonstrated the feasibility of directly depositing high- κ dielectrics on graphene using thermal ALD techniques, often by enhancing nucleation through a pre-H₂O treatment or by optimizing precursor-surface interactions, which effectively address the challenge of initiating film growth on the chemically inert graphene surface [21,22].

Given these considerations, selecting between thermal ALD and PEALD ultimately depends on the specific requirements of the application, as each method provides unique advantages. Thermal ALD is typically less invasive for graphene, reducing the likelihood of compromising its delicate structure. Alternatively, PEALD may offer

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shorter processing times, depending on the conditions, and is capable of producing high-quality, thin dielectric films [23]. Dielectrics deposited by PEALD are known for their high breakdown voltages [23] and their ability to form continuous ultrathin layers, which are less than 10 nm thick, on graphene and other 2D materials [9,24]. These ultrathin dielectric layers are particularly important in applications that require a low equivalent oxide thickness (EOT), such as gate-all-around nanosheet transistors or double-layer graphene modulators [1,4,25]. In these modulators, the overlapping top and bottom graphene electrodes form a capacitor, where a higher capacitance leads to a higher modulation efficiency [1,4,25]. Therefore, a very thin dielectric layer must be deposited on the graphene without damaging it. However, the plasma environment in PEALD, while effective in producing high-quality dielectrics, can be aggressive and poses a risk of damaging or etching the graphene layer [9]. The extent of this potential damage depends on the used plasma conditions and the used plasma gas. For example, oxygen (O_2) plasma often used in the deposition of dielectrics, produces highly reactive O_2 radicals that can significantly damage graphene, whereas plasma from gases such as hydrogen (H_2) [26] and nitrogen (N_2) [27] are less reactive, resulting in varying degrees of degradation depending on the plasma power and exposure time.

A study by Canto et al. demonstrated that a transferred hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) layer can effectively facilitate high-quality PEALD of Al_2O_3 on graphene, acting as an interface and protective barrier [24].

This approach is particularly promising because the graphene surface is protected by another 2D material, and the 2D–2D interface, bonded by van der Waals forces, preserves the quality of the graphene. However, the *ex situ* transfer process used in this method poses significant challenges for large-scale implementation.

Inspired by Canto's work [24], we developed an *in situ* process for depositing a protective layer instead of transferring it, which significantly improves the scalability of the process. The developed *in situ* method simplifies the deposition process, prevents defect formation and results in more uniform dielectric deposition. To evaluate the impact of this deposition technique on device performance, we fabricated top-gated graphene field-effect transistors (GFETs) on 150 mm wafers. Building on our recent work, where we demonstrated the process on $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ samples and focused on optimizing properties such as doping, mobility, and threshold voltage through dielectric thickness adjustments [28], we demonstrate in this study the low damage nature of the encapsulation method with a high electric field strength, a low EOT, and scale up to 150 mm wafers. To summarize, electrical measurements revealed that our method improved the mobility of the GFETs, achieved a dielectric strength greater than 11 MV/cm, and produced an EOT of less than 5 nm across the wafer.

Fig. 1. (A) Process scheme for AIOX protective coating and Al_2O_3 plasma ALD. Remote N_2 plasma with a low plasma dose prevents etching of graphene while ensuring its physical/chemical modification. The thin layer of AIOX provides efficient protection of the graphene against O_2 plasma during Al_2O_3 encapsulation. (B) Uniformity of the film thickness over a 150 mm wafer. A film thickness nonuniformity $< \pm 0.8 \%$ was achieved over the entire wafer surface. The data point locations are indicated. (C) Image of the Oxford Instruments Atomfab system. (D) Schematic of the Atomfab remote plasma source with powered (light gray) and grounded (dark gray) electrodes [patent application PCT/GB2019/052763]. This remote plasma method was used for low-damage deposition of both the protective AIOX layer and the Al_2O_3 dielectric (Figure reference: Knoops et al. [29]).

2. Results and discussions

We established a wafer-scale process for depositing dielectrics on graphene via an *in situ*-prepared, nonstoichiometric aluminum oxide (AIOX) protective layer. P-doped Si wafers with SiO₂ were used as substrates, onto which electrodes were patterned, followed by graphene transfer, patterning, etching, and resist removal; then, a thin AIOX layer (less than 3 nm) was grown using low-power N₂ plasma and a trimethylaluminum (TMA) precursor (see methods). The N₂-based plasma conditions were optimized to promote AIOX growth while preventing any observable damage to the graphene. This was followed by the deposition of a 9-nm Al₂O₃ layer using the same precursor with O₂ plasma, as shown in Fig. 1a. The total stack thickness of approximately 11.5 nm was measured via ellipsometry (Fig. 1b), assuming the stack has a refractive index of PEALD Al₂O₃ of 1.65. The thickness of the AIOX layer on graphene was determined in our recent study via transmission electron microscopy (TEM), where we estimated the number of cycles required to achieve an AIOX layer of approximately 3 nm based on the growth per cycle (GPC) extracted from our TEM analyses [28]. Furthermore, we refer to the protective layer as AIOX due to the measured composition of the film. The oxygen incorporation is due to the relatively low deposition rate and low plasma power of the process, which allows the absorption of O₂ from background gases and moisture (H₂O), as confirmed by TEM analysis [28]. Nevertheless, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) studies revealed that the N₂ plasma process introduces N and carbon (C) impurities into the material. For simplicity, we label this nonstoichiometric aluminum oxide as AIOX.

In the following section, we demonstrate that a sub-3 nm AIOX layer is sufficient to protect graphene from damage caused by O₂ plasma during the deposition of Al₂O₃. The deposition was conducted via an Oxford Instruments Atomfab PEALD system [29]. This system is equipped with a remote RF-driven capacitively coupled plasma (CCP) source and a grounded substrate table. In this configuration, the plasma generation electrodes and counter electrodes are positioned away from the substrate surface, ensuring that the grounded substrate remains outside the plasma generation zone, as depicted in Fig. 1d. This unique chamber design allows us to operate at very low doses and with remote plasma, thereby minimizing the risk of damage to graphene during the initial stages of deposition [29].

Raman spectra were recorded before and after the encapsulation process to assess the structural changes in the graphene due to encapsulation. These measurements were taken over 10 × 10 μm² areas distributed along the diameter of the wafer, as shown in the inset of Fig. 2a (see methods). The Raman analysis revealed significant differences between the samples with and without AIOX protective layer. For

the wafer encapsulated with PEALD without an AIOX layer, the Raman spectrum (Fig. 2a and SI Fig. 1a, red curve) shows a pronounced D peak, indicative of defects. This is confirmed by a significant increase in the I_D/I_G ratio (Fig. 2b and SI Fig. 1b–red), suggesting that O₂ plasma exposure during the process caused damage to the graphene lattice, which is consistent with findings from Canto’s work [24], where even mild and short O₂ plasma exposure has been shown to damage graphene in the absence of a protective layer. In contrast, the D peak of the wafer protected by an AIOX layer is negligible, with the I_D/I_G ratio remaining at pre-encapsulation levels (Fig. 2b, black before encapsulation and blue after encapsulation). This indicates minimal damage to the graphene. In addition, the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the 2D peak (Fig. 2c and SI Fig. 1c) remains low and similar to the pre-encapsulation value, reflecting the minimal strain induced by the AIOX seed layer. Further analysis reveals that the AIOX seed layer serves not only as a protective barrier but also influences the electronic properties of graphene. As demonstrated in our previous work [28], adjusting the thickness of the AIOX layer allows the doping level to be controlled, with thicker layers causing a noticeable shift in the Dirac point. However, layers thinner than ~2 nm offer insufficient coverage, resulting in partial protection and observable damage to the Raman spectra after PEALD (SI Fig. 2). In contrast, thicker AIOX layers (>3 nm) provide more effective protection [28]. We also found that increasing the plasma dose by raising power and extending the exposure time introduces defects (SI Fig. 2), further emphasizing the importance of optimizing both AIOX thickness and plasma conditions. The exact mechanism that enables uniform AIOX deposition on graphene is not fully understood, but it is likely aided by the presence of grain boundaries and defects in the CVD-grown and transferred graphene, which provide nucleation sites for ALD. Additionally, physisorption of TMA and partial surface activation under plasma-enhanced conditions may contribute to film initiation. These combined effects allow the conformal growth of AIOX even without deliberate surface functionalization. Further investigation into this mechanism could be a valuable direction for future studies.

Next, we fabricated top-gated GFETs on wafers with the dielectric stack deposited via the developed technique to evaluate the impact on device performance, as described in the Methods section. Six-terminal Hall bars were used as test structures, with the devices operating as three-terminal FETs. The inner terminals, shown in Fig. 3a and b, were used to measure the effective voltage difference (V_{diff}) across the graphene channel, which minimizes errors due to the contact resistances when calculating the device mobility (see Methods) [30].

Measurements were conducted on six dies, with 5–6 devices tested on each die along the diameter of the wafer, both before and after encapsulation. Fig. 3c shows the transfer characteristics (I_{DS} vs. V_{BG}) of

Fig. 2. (A) Raman spectra across the wafer radius (R) (inset) for the Gr/SiO₂/Si wafers before and after Al₂O₃ deposition, with (blue) and without (red) an AIOX protective layer. (b) $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ across wafer R for the Gr/SiO₂/Si wafers. (c) FWHM (2D) across the wafer radius (R) for the Gr/SiO₂/Si wafer. ‘Before’ and ‘after’ refer to Raman measurements taken on the same graphene sample before and after AIOX/Al₂O₃ deposition, respectively, to ensure that the comparison is not affected by variation between samples. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. (A) Schematic of a back-gated GFET in a four-point probe configuration (see Methods). (b) Top-view optical image of a back-gated device. (c) Transfer curves of back-gate measurements for six devices before (black) and after (blue) encapsulation. Evaluation of (d) hole and (e) electron mobility over the wafer radius (R). Measurements were performed on six dies. Five to six devices were tested on each die along R , before (black) and after encapsulation (blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. (A) Top-gated current–voltage plots (sweep: 5 V to +5 V) with constant back-gate voltage for a GFET. Inset: Schematic of a back-gated GFET in a two-point configuration with bottom source and drain contacts and an ALOX- Al_2O_3 dielectric stack. Each curve represents a different back-gate voltage from -30 V to $+30$ V in steps of 10 V. (b) Top gate voltage at the charge neutrality point (CNP) as a function of the applied back-gate voltage. Statistical extraction of (c) the dielectric constant and (d) EOT from the double-gate measurement over R . The measurements were carried out on 6 dies, with 5 devices being tested on each die along R .

the devices before and after encapsulation. A significant increase in hole mobility was observed after encapsulation (Fig. 3d). Notably, the electron mobility (Fig. 3e) could only be extracted after encapsulation. Before encapsulation, the Dirac voltage (V_{Dirac}) exceeded 75 V, which was beyond the measurement capabilities of our probe station. After dielectric deposition, V_{Dirac} shifted negatively by more than 75 V. This aligns with our recent results [28], where we observed an n-doping effect in the graphene channel after AlOX deposition. The substantial increase in current and mobility can be attributed to the presence of positive fixed charges in the AlOX layer, which may be related to the nitrogen content within the dielectric film. These charges accumulate excess electrons at the interface between the AlOX and the graphene channel, leading to n-type doping, a negative shift in V_{Dirac} , and, consequently, an increase in the transistors' on-current and mobility [28]. The improved mobility can also be attributed to reduced phonon and Coulomb scattering, and less water and oxygen molecules being adsorbed on the graphene surface after encapsulation²⁵.

Double-gate measurements were conducted with the back-gate held at constant voltages of -30 V, -20 V, -10 V, 0 V, $+10$ V, $+20$ V, and $+30$ V while the top-gate was swept from -5 to 5 V in a two-probe configuration. The resulting top-gate transfer curves on a single device are presented in Fig. 4a. To determine the dielectric constant ϵ_{rTG} of the capping (AlOX/Al₂O₃) layer, we analyzed the curves in Fig. 4a by plotting the top-gate voltage at the charge neutrality point (CNP) against the applied back-gate voltage. The slope from the linear fit of this plot corresponds to the ratio of the back-gate capacitance (90 nm SiO₂) to the top-gate capacitance (11.5 nm AlOX/Al₂O₃), enabling us to calculate ϵ_{rTG} (see methods). Fig. 4b shows the linear fit derived from the minimum values of the transfer curves, with a slope of 0.055 ± 0.002 . Assuming an ϵ_{rBG} of 3.9 for SiO₂, this slope yields a dielectric constant of 9.06 ± 0.33 for the 11.5 nm capping layer and a top-gate equivalent oxide thickness (EOT) of 4.93 ± 0.18 nm. These calculations were conducted on 35 devices distributed across the wafer, and the box plots of the extracted k values and EOT are shown in Fig. 4c and d, respectively.

We then performed top-gate (I_D vs. V_{TG}) measurements in a two-probe configuration, which revealed negligible hysteresis and maximum hole and electron mobilities of $1480 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ and $1150 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, respectively (Fig. 5a). These mobilities are lower than those obtained from back-gate measurements, largely due to partial gating, where only a portion of the graphene channel between the contact pads is covered by the local top gate, and the increased contact resistance of the two-probe configuration. The top gate measurements were limited to a two-probe configuration, as a fifth probe was not available to apply the top gate bias. In contrast, the back-gate measurements used the chuck as

a global back gate, allowing all four available probes to be used in a four-probe configuration. The uncovered regions and contact resistance introduce additional series resistance, which further affects the mobility measurement [30,31]. Although correcting for this resistance would result in a higher extracted mobility, we did not perform this correction, as it would not provide additional insights relevant to this work. The evolution of the top-gate leakage current with increasing top-gate voltage is shown in Fig. 5b. The gate dielectric remained stable up to 13 V, with leakage current densities below $1.5 \text{ fA}/\mu\text{m}^2$. Beyond this voltage, a significant increase in current was observed, indicating the onset of breakdown. This corresponds to an electric field strength of $11.44 \pm 0.3 \text{ MV/cm}$. The dielectric strength was evaluated on 35 devices across the wafer and plotted in a box plot in Fig. 5c. The dielectric strength exceeded 11 MV/cm for all the devices. This high electric field strength is consistent with the best values reported in the literature [32], which suggests the absence of pinholes and confirms the high quality of the dielectric.

3. Summary and conclusions

This work addresses the challenge of depositing high-quality dielectrics on graphene by developing an *in situ* process to form a protective AlOX layer, which enables PEALD of Al₂O₃ without damaging the graphene surface. Traditional methods often involve complex, *ex situ* steps that are difficult to scale, especially for large wafers. Our approach eliminates these issues, keeping graphene intact and ensuring uniform dielectric deposition across 150 mm wafers, as confirmed by Raman spectroscopy, which revealed minimal structural changes. We then fabricated top-gated GFETs using our encapsulation method, which resulted in improved performance, including increased mobility and dielectric strength. Our devices achieved a dielectric strength of over 11 MV/cm and an EOT below 5 nm, confirming the effectiveness of the protective layer in creating a high-quality dielectric for GFETs. This scalable, wafer-level process preserves the electronic properties of graphene and enables ultrathin dielectrics suitable for next-generation electronic and photonic applications.

4. Methods

Device fabrication: P-doped Si wafers (150 mm) with resistivities ranging from 1 to 20 $\Omega \text{ cm}$ and a 90 nm layer of thermally oxidized SiO₂ were used as substrates. The metal electrodes were patterned via optical lithography with a double layer of LOR 3A resist (Micro Resist Technology) and AZ5214E photoresist (MicroChemicals). Following the lithography step, 5 nm of titanium (Ti) and 15 nm of palladium (Pd)

Fig. 5. Top-gated electrical data of GFETs in the two-point probe configuration. (a) Top-gated current–voltage transfer curves for GFETs. Inset: Schematic of a top-gated GFET in a two-point probe configuration. (b) Top-gate leakage versus gate voltage for three devices as an example to show that leakage increases significantly at 13 V, where the irreversible breakdown voltage occurs. Inset: Leakage current of the devices. (c) Assessment of the electric field strength over R . Measurements were made on 6 dies with 5 devices tested on each die along R .

were deposited via electron-beam (e-beam) evaporation. The unwanted metal was then removed via a lift-off process in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). The prepatterned substrates were subsequently sent to Graphenea for full wafer-scale transfer of chemical vapor deposition (CVD)-grown single-layer graphene. After receiving the wafer back from Graphenea, the graphene layer was patterned and etched via a positive lithography process with an AZ5214E photoresist. Low-power reactive ion etching (RIE) with oxygen plasma was employed to etch the graphene. Finally, the photoresist was stripped by immersing the substrates in acetone at 50 °C for 60 min. A dielectric layer was subsequently deposited on the wafers. The protective layer deposition step used trimethylaluminum (TMA) as the precursor alternated with N₂ plasma exposures, whereas the Al₂O₃ deposition step employed TMA and O₂ plasma. The deposition process was conducted using an Oxford Instruments Atomfab PEALD system, which features a remote RF-driven capacitively coupled plasma (CCP) source and a grounded table. In this tool, the plasma generation electrodes and counter electrodes are situated away from the substrate surface, ensuring that the grounded substrate does not participate in the plasma generation area [patent application PCT/GB2019/052763]. An initial ALOX layer of approximately 3 nm thickness was deposited at a substrate temperature of 200 °C, using an RF forward power of 50 W. The chamber gas mixture used a 3:4 ratio of N₂/Ar gas mixture. The growth cycle time was approximately 1.3 s per cycle, with each cycle including a 100 ms exposure to the N₂/Ar plasma. An Al₂O₃ layer was subsequently deposited at a substrate temperature of 300 °C without exposing the wafer to the atmosphere between these steps. During the temperature adjustment, the wafer was stored in the load lock. In this second deposition step, a plasma gas mixture of O₂ and Ar gas at a 3:4 ratio was used. The growth cycle time for this step was approximately 1 s, with each cycle involving 100 ms of O₂/Ar plasma exposure. Next, *in situ* gas annealing was carried out in the ALD chamber at a table temperature of 350 °C, utilizing a gas mixture of N₂ and H₂ in a 20:1 ratio and a set pressure of 261 mTorr. The final stack thickness, as measured via ellipsometry, was approximately 11.5 nm (Fig. 1b). Finally, the top gate electrodes were patterned via negative optical lithography with an AZ5214E photoresist. This was followed by the deposition of 5 nm of Ti and 15 nm of Pd via electron-beam evaporation, with the excess metal removed through a lift-off process.

Raman: Raman spectroscopy was conducted via a WiTec alpha300R Raman imaging microscope equipped with a 532 nm laser operating at 1 mW power, with an integration time of 0.5 s for each point during the scan. The analysis was performed before and after the deposition of the dielectric layers to evaluate the quality of the graphene. Measurements were taken on 10 × 10 μm² areas distributed across various points along the wafer's diameter, with each area consisting of 90 spectra. The resulting spectra were subsequently analyzed via Lorentzian function fitting to determine the ratio of the D to G peak intensities and the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the 2D peak.

Electrical characterization: The electrical characterization of the GFETs was performed in a Cascade Summit 12000 semiautomatic probe station, which was connected to a Hewlett Packard 4156 B precision semiconductor parameter analyzer and a Hewlett Packard E5250A low leakage switch mainframe. Carrier mobility for globally back-gated devices was assessed via four-terminal measurements. The calculation was performed via the following equation:

$$\mu_{BG} = (\partial(I_{DS} / V_{diff}) / \partial V_{BGS}) \cdot L_{12} t_{BG} / (W_{channel} \cdot \epsilon_{rBG} \cdot \epsilon_0)$$

where I_{DS} represents the drain-source current, V_{diff} denotes the voltage difference between the inner contacts, V_{BGS} represents the voltage difference between the back gate and source, t_{BG} represents the thickness of the global back gate dielectric (90 nm of SiO₂), L_{12} represents the distance between the inner contacts, W represents the width of the channel, ϵ_{rBG} represents the dielectric constant of the back-gate dielectric (thermal SiO₂, which is 3.9), and ϵ_0 represents the vacuum permittivity. The

channel has a length of approximately 40 μm and a width of 10 μm. The measurement was conducted with an applied drain-source voltage of 100 mV.

The dielectric constant (ϵ_{rTG}) of the ALOX/Al₂O₃ stack was determined from dual-gate electrical measurements (Fig. 4) by plotting the top gate voltage at the charge neutrality point (CNP) as a function of the applied back-gate voltage. The slope of the linear fit in this plot corresponds to:

$$Slope = C_{BG} / C_{TG}$$

where C_{BG} is the capacitance of the back gate and where C_{TG} is the capacitance of the top gate. From this, the dielectric constant ϵ_r can be calculated via the following equation:

$$\epsilon_{rTG} = (1 / slope) \cdot \epsilon_{rBG} \cdot \frac{t_{TG}}{t_{BG}}$$

where t_{TG} is the thickness of the top-gate dielectric stack (ALOX/Al₂O₃) and is approximately 11.5 nm.

After the dielectric constant was determined, the equivalent oxide thickness (EOT) was calculated via the following equation:

$$EOT = t_{TG} \cdot \left(\epsilon_{rBG} / \epsilon_{rTG} \right)$$

To ensure an accurate estimation of the electric field strength, breakdown voltage measurements were performed at multiple points along the diameter of the wafer. The local dielectric thickness at each point was obtained from ellipsometry mapping, and the electric field was calculated as the ratio of breakdown voltage to local thickness, according to the following equation:

$$E = \frac{V_{BD}}{t_{TG}}$$

where V_{BD} is the breakdown voltage and t_{TG} is the locally measured dielectric thickness at that point.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sarah Riazimehr: Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation. **Ardeshir Esteki:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Martin Otto:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Michael Powell:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Gordon Rinke:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Bianca Robertz:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Zhenxing Wang:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Max C. Lemme:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Katie Hore:** Writing – review & editing. **Harm Knoops:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mssp.2025.109829>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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